

Legends for Movies and Supplemental Datasets | Hamm *et al.* (2022)

Supplemental Data S2. Spreadsheet with normalized data (mean GFP values) for all cell lineage trajectories shown in the paper.

Supplemental Data S3. Spreadsheet with raw data (mean GFP values) for all cell lineage trajectories shown in the paper.

Supplemental Movie Legends

Movie S1. Response of wild-type cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC1801 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S2. Response of wild-type cells to 0.005% H₂O₂. Representative MTC1801 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S3. Response of wild-type cells to 500 mM NaCl. Representative MTC1801 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S4. Response of wild-type cells to a change in media from LB pH 6.5 to LB pH 6.25. Representative MTC1801 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S5. Response of RsbRA-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC1671 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S6. Response of RsbRA-only cells to 0.005% H₂O₂. Representative MTC1761 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP

channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S7. Response of RsbRA-only cells to 500 mM NaCl. Representative MTC1761 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S8. Response of RsbRA-only cells to a change in media from LB pH 6.5 to LB pH 6.25. Representative MTC1761 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S9. Response of RsbRB-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC1673 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S10. Response of RsbRB-only cells to 0.005% H₂O₂. Representative MTC1763 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S11. Response of RsbRB-only cells to 500 mM NaCl. Representative MTC1763 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S12. Response of RsbRB-only cells to a change in media from LB pH 6.5 to LB pH 6.25. Representative MTC1763 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S13. Response of RsbRC-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC1675 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP

channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S14. Response of RsbRC-only cells to 0.005% H₂O₂. Representative MTC1765 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S15. Response of RsbRC-only cells to 500 mM NaCl. Representative MTC1765 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S16. Response of RsbRC-only cells to a change in media from LB pH 6.5 to LB pH 6.25. Representative MTC1765 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S17. Response of RsbRD-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC1677 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S18. Response of RsbRD-only cells to 0.005% H₂O₂. Representative MTC1767 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S19. Response of RsbRD-only cells to 500 mM NaCl. Representative MTC1767 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S20. Response of RsbRD-only cells to a change in media from LB pH 6.5 to LB pH 6.25. Representative MTC1767 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the top of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the bottom of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown

in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S21. Response of RsbRC/A-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2540 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S22. Response of RsbRA/C-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2541 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S23. Response of RsbRC/B-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2542 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S24. Response of RsbRB/C-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2543 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the

feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S25. Response of RsbRD/A-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2544 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S26. Response of RsbRA/D-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2545 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S27. Response of RsbRB/A-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2546 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)

Movie S28. Response of RsbRA/B-only cells to 2% Ethanol. Representative MTC2547 cell lineages are shown, with the mother cells oriented toward the bottom of the frame and the feeding/waste channel toward the top of the frame. The images were captured in the GFP channel to visualize the PrsbV-mNeonGreen reporter. Time is shown in hours and minutes, and the introduction of stressor corresponds with the appearance of the label. (AVI)